

Comparative Immunology, Microbiology and Infectious Diseases

Urban birds: an important source of antimicrobial resistant Salmonella strains in Central Spain

--Manuscript Draft--

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Corresponding Author:	Barbara Martin-Maldonado, L.V. GREFA Majadahonda, Madrid SPAIN
First Author:	Barbara Martin-Maldonado, L.V.
Order of Authors:	Barbara Martin-Maldonado, L.V. Santiago Vega, PhD Aida Mencia-Gutierrez, LV Laura Lorenzo-Rebenaque, Veterinary Degree Cristina de Frutos, Ph.D. Fernando González, LV Luis Revuelta, PhD Clara Marin, PhD
Abstract:	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the most important threats of the 21st century. Wild birds have been described as reservoirs of AMR in different bacterial species, such as Salmonella spp. Privation of food, climate change and overpopulation have forced many wild species to modify their feeding habits, attending urban areas. In this context, the aim of this study was to study Salmonella presence, as well as related AMR in urban birds that inhabit the city and its surroundings. A total of 300 urban birds were sampled for Salmonella detection according to the ISO 6579-1:2017 (Annex D) recommendations, and serotyping was carried out according to the White-Kauffman-Le Minor scheme. Antimicrobial susceptibility was tested following 2013/652/EU Decision guides. Wild birds analysed were positive for Salmonella in 12.3% of cases, with white storks fed in landfills as the most Salmonella prevalent species ($p < 0.05$). The most common serovars isolated were zoonotic (<i>S. Enteritidis</i> , <i>S. Typhimurium</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i> monophasic variant). From Salmonella isolated strains, 40.5% were resistant and the most prevalent AMRs found in urban birds were ciprofloxacin (36.4%), nalidixic acid (36.4%) and colistin (27.3%). The scientific community, public administration and population in general should work together to control antimicrobial administration and drug waste management in order to decrease the development and spread of AMR.
Response to Reviewers:	

Frederic Beugnet and Congli Yuan
Co-Editors-in-Chief
Comparative Immunology, Microbiology and Infectious diseases

Submission date: 09-October-2019

Dear Co-Editors,

I am writing to submit our manuscript entitled, "Landfills: an important source of antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* for urban birds" for consideration as a full paper. We investigated the occurrence of *Salmonella* spp and the associated antimicrobial resistances in five different urban bird species in the Community of Madrid. We analysed our results with several factors, such as the biology, diet, age, and geographical origin of all the animals included in the study, and determined that contaminated waste from landfills represents an important reservoir of antimicrobial resistance for urban species. This fact becomes important when hundreds of urban birds, mainly white storks and lesser black-backed gulls, feed on these sites daily, increasing the risk of transmission of antimicrobial resistance.

Given the alarming increase in antimicrobial resistance, we believe that the findings presented in this study will appeal to the scientists who subscribe to Comparative Immunology, Microbiology and Infectious Diseases. Although prior research has described the presence of antimicrobial resistance in wildlife, our findings will enable your readers to understand the role of landfill sites and the need for more effective waste management and awareness raising on the issue.

This manuscript examines a different aspect of the factors involved in the acquisition and spread of resistant bacteria in birds, an issue that had previously been explored in the following papers also published by Elsevier:

- Jurado-Tarifa, E., Torralbo, A., Borge, C., Cerdà-Cuéllar, M., Ayats, T., Carbonero, A., & García-Bocanegra, I. (2016). Genetic diversity and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* strains isolated from decoys and raptors. *Comparative immunology, microbiology and infectious diseases*, *48*, 14-21.
- Dobbin, G., Hariharan, H., Daoust, P. Y., Hariharan, S., Heaney, S., Coles, M., Price, L. & Muckle, C. A. (2005). Bacterial flora of free-living double-crested cormorant (*Phalacrocorax auritus*) chicks on Prince Edward Island, Canada, with reference to enteric bacteria and antibiotic resistance. *Comparative immunology, microbiology and infectious diseases*, *28*, 71-82.
- Dipineto, L., Bossa, L. M. D. L., Pace, A., Russo, T. P., Gargiulo, A., Ciccarelli, F., Raia, P., Caputo, V., & Fioretti, A. (2015). Microbiological survey of birds of prey pellets. *Comparative immunology, microbiology and infectious diseases*, *41*, 49-53.

The co-authors of this manuscript confirm that it has not been previously published and is not currently under consideration by any other journal. Additionally, all the authors have approved the contents of this paper and agreed to the CIMID's submission policies.

To the best of our knowledge, none of the above-suggested persons have any conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

Each named author has substantially contributed to conducting the underlying research and drafting this manuscript. Additionally, to the best of our knowledge, the named authors have no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

Sincerely,

Bárbara Martín-Maldonado

Corresponding Author

DVM, PhD-Student

GREFA Wildlife Hospital

Postal Address: C/ Monte del Pilar, s/n. CP: 28220, Majadahonda (Madrid). SPAIN

E-mail Address: barbara@grefa.org

Tel: +34 91 6387550

Clara Marin

DVM, PhD, Professor

Additional Contact

Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad CEU-Cardenal Herrera

Postal Address: C/ Tirant Lo Blanc, 7. CP: 46115, Alfara del Patriarca (Valencia). SPAIN

E-mail Address: clara.marin@uchceu.es

Tel: +34 96 1369000 (ext 66107)

Dear Rasika Paul James,

The authors of this work would like to thank the editor and reviewer for the support in publishing this study. We really appreciate it. The reviewer's comments have been included in the manuscript as follows:

Reviewer #3:

The authors of this work want to thank the reviewer for the support in publishing this work.

Martín-Maldonado, B. and his/her colleagues (Manuscript Number CIMID-D-19-00312), present an interesting study of the prevalence of *Salmonella* in 300 urban birds in the Community of Madrid in Spain. There are a total of 37 *Salmonella* isolates from eight serovars identified by the standard microbiological analytic approach. Additional antimicrobial resistance assay was conducted to check the MIC for a list of 14 antimicrobials. The overall study is well-written and technical sound. Considering a significant number of isolates were resistant to quinolone and colistin, also very limited number of *Salmonella* isolates found in this study, the whole genomic sequencing would be an ideal approach to dissect the genetic determinants for those particular resistant strains, as well as the genetic relationship for those strains within the same serovars.

The authors of this study totally agree with the reviewer comment, in fact, based on the results obtained in this study, a new project has been presented to find financing to expand the research, and among the objectives are, the study of strains genomic sequencing, as well as the study of the genetic relationship for isolated strains.

Last, the title should be changed. Even though some of urban birds were living besides the landfills, it remains unclear how landfills play a role in emergence of antimicrobial resistance bacteria or *Salmonella*. Further environmental samplings or investigation in landfills is needed. The landfill story in the discussion is OK.

According to the reviewer suggestion, the title has been modified in the manuscript ("*Urban birds: an important source of antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains in Central Spain*")

Minor point:

- **Change "antibiotic" to "antimicrobial".** The antibiotic has been changed in the manuscript (Lines 194, 201, 211, 212, 214, 216, 217, 279, 290, 293)
- **The exact time period for the samplings or study should be included in the material and method section.** The period of sampling has been included in the manuscript (Line 86: "*from June 2018 to January 2019*")

HIGHLIGHTS

- Urban birds are reservoirs and disseminators of antimicrobial resistance.
- The increase in urban waste is an important source of food for urban birds.
- Landfills have the perfect conditions for AMR development and transmission.
- Colistin represents the last chance against pan-resistant enterobacteria.

Urban birds: an important source of antimicrobial resistant

Salmonella strains in Central Spain.

Martín-Maldonado, B.^{a,e*}, Vega, S.^{d,e}, Mencía-Gutiérrez, A.^{a,e}, Lorenzo-Rebenaque, L.^d, de Frutos, C.^b, González, F.^{a,e}, Revuelta, L.^{c,e}, Marin, C.^{d,e}

^aHospital de Fauna Salvaje. Grupo de Rehabilitación de la Fauna Autóctona y su Hábitat (GREFA). Madrid, Spain.

^bLaboratorio Central de Veterinaria. Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación. Madrid, Spain.

^cDepartamento de Fisiología Animal. Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Madrid, Spain.

^dInstituto de Ciencias Biomédicas. Departamento de Producción Animal, Sanidad Animal y Ciencia y Tecnología de los Alimentos. Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad CEU-Cardenal Herrera. Valencia, Spain.

^eGrupo de Estudio de la Medicina y Conservación de la Fauna Silvestre (GEMAS), Spain.

Corresponding author: Bárbara Martín-Maldonado. E-mail address: bmmjimenezvet@gmail.com Postal address: Hospital de Fauna Salvaje, GREFA. C/ Monte del Pilar, s/n. CP 28220, Majadahonda (Madrid), SPAIN.

HIGHLIGHTS

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the most important threats of the 21st century. Wild birds have been described as reservoirs of AMR in different bacterial species, such as *Salmonella* spp. Privation of food, climate change and overpopulation have forced many wild species to modify their feeding habits, attending urban areas. In this context, the aim of this study was to study *Salmonella* presence, as well as related AMR in urban birds that inhabit the city and its surroundings. A total of 300 urban birds were sampled for *Salmonella* detection according to the ISO 6579-1:2017 (Annex D) recommendations, and serotyping was carried out according to the White-Kauffman-Le Minor scheme. Antimicrobial susceptibility was tested

30 following 2013/652/EU Decision guides. Wild birds analysed were positive for *Salmonella* in
31 12.3% of cases, with white storks fed in landfills as the most *Salmonella* prevalent species
32 ($p < 0.05$). The most common serovars isolated were zoonotic (*S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*
33 and *S. Typhimurium* monophasic variant). From *Salmonella* isolated strains, 40.5% were
34 resistant to the most prevalent AMRs found in urban birds were ciprofloxacin (36.4%), nalidixic
35 acid (36.4%) and colistin (27.3%). The scientific community, public administration and
36 population in general should work together to control antimicrobial administration and drug
37 waste management in order to decrease the development and spread of AMR.

38

39 **KEYWORDS**

40 Landfills; urban birds; white stork; *Salmonella*; AMR; quinolones; colistin.

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 One health, the relationship between human, animal and environmental health, is one of the
44 most important interdisciplinary integrations of medicine [1]. The phenomenon of urbanisation
45 has a profound impact on ecological systems [2], and forces animals to change their feeding
46 habits, nesting areas or even migration patterns. A multitude of species coexist today in urban
47 areas (pigeons, sparrows, starlings, lizards, geckos, or even raccoons and wild boars), using
48 the resources that human activity provides them to live, feed and reproduce [3].

49 The increase in human populations results in an increase in daily-renewed urban waste: meat,
50 fish, chicken, fruit, etc. Many studies document the use of landfills by different species of wild
51 bird, as dumping sites and supplier markets are excellent areas for these species to feed easily
52 [4-6]. Moreover, the constant availability of food resources in cities and milder winter
53 temperatures, due to climate change, allow certain wild species to make shorter migrations or
54 even halt their migration to form resident populations as urban birds (**UB**) [7]. In Spain, gulls and
55 storks are two examples of this situation [5,8,9].

56 However, feeding based in wastes can favour the development of some nutritional diseases
57 (vitamin and others nutrient deficiencies), intoxications (botulism, salmonellosis, colibacillosis,

58 etc.), the bioaccumulation of metals as well as other noxious substances (lead, pesticides, etc.),
59 or pathologies caused by waste such as plastics [10-12]. Moreover, poor waste management
60 favours the accumulation of harmful substances in landfills, mostly drugs such as anti-
61 inflammatory or antimicrobials. In this context, landfills can be a source of multi-resistant strains
62 of many bacterial species for UB, which can become a source of contamination [13,14].

63 Antimicrobial resistance (**AMR**) is one of the most important threats in the 21st century, with
64 implications of increased morbidity, mortality and cost rates [15,16]. Moreover, numerous AMR
65 have been reported in *Enterobacteria* isolated from untreated urban wildlife, such as *Salmonella*
66 spp. Resistant bacteria can be spread over large distances or increase the likelihood of uptake
67 with close contact, as UB is an important vector for AMR [17,21].

68 The widespread distribution of *Salmonella* in birds makes them a great indicator for the AMR
69 situation in wildlife, as it can colonise the intestine of most homoeothermic animals, humans
70 included. *Salmonella* is the second most prevalent zoonosis in the EU, with more than 91,000
71 cases reported in 2017 [22]. Generally, the clinical signs are those of acute gastroenteritis, but
72 salmonellosis can also cause severe syndromes such as Reiter's Syndrome and Typhoid Fever
73 in children and elderly people [23]. Wild animals might play a significant role in transmission of
74 the pathogen in the environment; wild birds have been described as an asymptomatic reservoir
75 of *Salmonella* and they are considered an important vector for the transfer of AMR bacteria in
76 cattle, livestock and the environment [20,24]. The range of *Salmonella* detection in UB in
77 Europe varies from 0% to 50% depending on the species, being more prevalent in gulls and
78 storks [20,24]. More isolated serotypes in wild birds were *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Indiana*
79 and *S. Enteritidis*, some of most frequently isolated serotypes in human salmonellosis outbreaks
80 [20,22,25]. In this context, the aim of this study was to investigate *Salmonella* presence, as well
81 as related AMR in wild birds that inhabit the city and its surroundings.

82

83 **2. Material and methods**

84 **2.1. Study population**

85 For this study, different UB species from the Community of Madrid (Spain) were sampled upon
86 their admission to a wildlife rescue centre (GREFA, Madrid), from June 2018 to January 2019,

87 following the principles of animal care published by Spanish Royal Decree 53/2013 (BOE,
88 2013). The birds' admission to the centre was due to several causes: nest fall, trauma and
89 others causes such as botulism, gizzard impaction or being trapped in buildings. Birds were
90 identified by species and classified by age as young (including nestlings and fledglings) or
91 adults. Individuals belonging to the following species were included in the study: white storks
92 (*Ciconia ciconia*), lesser black-backed gulls (*Larus fuscus*), common wood pigeons (*Columba*
93 *palumbus*), common starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*) and house sparrows (*Passer domesticus*). For
94 the purpose of this study, the environment where they inhabit was recorded as urban or rural
95 areas. In the case of gulls, urban individuals were always related to landfills. For white storks,
96 the environment where they inhabit were three: urban, rural area and landfills.

97 Once all the information related to the bird was recorded, a first examination was performed at
98 the hospital and the clinical signs were recorded. When necessary, haematology, biochemistry,
99 radiography and ultrasonography were performed. From each animal, a cloacal swab was taken
100 at each first examination, before any treatment was administered. Swabs were maintained at
101 4°C and processed within 24 hours after collection.

102

103 **2.2. Microbiological analysis**

104 The collected samples were analysed according to ISO 6579-1:2017 (Annex D) [26]. First, the
105 samples were pre-enriched in 1:10 vol/vol buffered peptone water 2.5% (Scharlau, Barcelona,
106 Spain) and then incubated at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 18 ± 2 h. Then, 100 μL of pre-enriched samples were
107 transferred onto Semi-Solid Modification Rappaport Vassiliadis (MSRV, Difco, Valencia, Spain)
108 and incubated at 41.5°C for 24 to 48 h. The culture obtained in MSRV was inoculated onto a
109 chromogenic agar specific for detection of C8-esterase activity (ASAP, bioMerieux, Marcy
110 l'Étoile, France), and incubated at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 24-48 hours. After incubation, positive colonies of
111 *Salmonella* were streaked onto the surface of pre-dried nutrient agar plates (International
112 Organisation for Standardisation) $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Moreover, *Salmonella* strains isolated were
113 serotyped at the National Reference Laboratory for Animal Salmonellosis (Madrid, Spain). The
114 method used for serotyping was antigenic agglutination with specific antisera according to the
115 White-Kauffmann-Le Minor scheme [27].

116

117 Finally, the AMR was determined at the National Reference Laboratory for Animal
118 Salmonellosis (Madrid, Spain). For the procedure, ISO 20776-1:2006 recommendations were
119 followed, performing a Mueller-Hinton broth micro dilution to determine the minimum inhibitory
120 concentration (MIC), using the epidemiologic breakpoints from the EUCAST recommendations
121 [28,29]. According to the 2013/652/EU Decision [30], a panel of 14 antimicrobials were tested
122 from different families, including two quinolones: ciprofloxacin (CIP) and nalidixic acid (NA); four
123 b-lactams: ampicillin (AMP), cefoxitin (FOX), ceftazidime (CAZ) and meropenem (MEM); one
124 phenicol: chloramphenicol (CHL); one sulphonamide: sulfamethoxazole (RL); one polymyxin:
125 colistin (COL); one macrolide: azithromycin (AZM); one glycylicycline: tigecycline (TGC); one
126 aminoglycoside: gentamycin (GN); one pyrimidine: trimethoprim (W) and one tetracycline:
127 tetracycline (TCY). Azithromycin and sulfamethoxazole have no defined breakpoint, so they
128 could not be interpreted. A multidrug-resistant (MDR) strain was considered when the isolate
129 was non-susceptible to at least one antimicrobial agent in two or more antimicrobial categories.

130

131 **2.3. Statistical analysis**

132 Statistical analysis was performed using a commercially available software application (SPSS
133 21.0 software package; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, 2002). A General Lineal Model was performed
134 to assess the relationship between *Salmonella* presence and different UB species
135 characteristics (age, pathology and environment). Moreover, a chi-squared test was performed
136 to study the relationship between *Salmonella* and their AMR. Finally, a chi-squared test was
137 done to study the relationship between each serovar and its UB origin. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was
138 considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

139

140 **3. Results**

141 From June 2018 to January 2019, a total of 300 UB from the Community of Madrid (Spain) were
142 sampled: white storks (n=100), lesser black-backed gulls (n=25), common wood pigeons
143 (n=100), house sparrows (n=50) and common starlings (n=25). According to bird age, 72%

144 (n=216) of the admissions were young and 28% (n=84) adults. In addition, the reasons for
145 admission to the hospital were mainly related to nest fall (134/300) and trauma (92/300).
146 However, 24.7% did not present any pathology.

147 From all animals sampled, 12.3% (37/300) were positive for *Salmonella* spp. A wide range of
148 *Salmonella* infection rate was observed depending on the UB specie analysed ($p=0.002$). From
149 *Salmonella*-positive birds (n=37), the most infected species were white storks (59.5%, n=22),
150 followed by common wood pigeons (18.9%, n=7), lesser black-backed gulls (13.3%, n=5),
151 house sparrows (5.4%, n=2) and common starlings (2.7%, n=1). According to age, 73% (27/37)
152 of positive birds were young and 27% (10/37) adults. In addition, pathologies were mainly
153 related to nest fall (19/37) and trauma (8/37). It is important to highlight that no significant
154 differences were found between the bird age or pathology observed and *Salmonella* status of
155 the animal ($p>0.05$).

156 When the relationship between *Salmonella* status and the environment inhabited by UB was
157 analysed, no statistical differences were found between *Salmonella* prevalence obtained in
158 urban areas assessed (outskirts or city). However, when white storks had access to landfills,
159 statistical differences were found ($p=0.031$). From all *Salmonella* infected white storks (22/100),
160 77.3% (17/22) inhabited landfills, 18.2% (4/22) the city centre and 4.5% (1/22) the outskirts. In
161 the case of lesser black-backed gulls, the only five positive individuals were related to landfill
162 areas. Nevertheless, no statistical differences were found in that studied species.

163 The most prevalent serovar isolated from UB was *S. Enteritidis* (43.2%, n=16). From all *S.*
164 *Enteritidis* strains isolated, 50% (8/16) were isolated from white storks feeding in landfills.
165 Moreover, *S. Enteritidis* serovar was also isolated in white stork from the city environment (n=2)
166 and outskirts (n=1). The second and third most prevalent serovars were *S. Typhimurium*
167 (16.2%, n=6) and *S. Typhimurium* monophasic variant (mST) (13.5%, n=5). *S. Typhimurium*
168 was isolated from common wood pigeons (n=4), white storks (n=1) and gulls (n=1) and, mST
169 from white storks (n=3), gulls (n=1) and sparrows (n=1). The less prevalent serovars isolated in
170 this study were: *S. Chester*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Kentucky* and *S. Abony* (5.4%, n=2, respectively)
171 and, *S. Pomona* and *S. Saintpaul* (2.7%, n=1, respectively). *Salmonella* serovars isolated from
172 different UB species are summarised in Table 1.

173 **Table 1.** Percentage of each *Salmonella* serovar isolated by species.

174

<i>Salmonella</i> serovars	n	Total (%)	Species (%)				
			White storks	Common wood pigeons	Lesser black-backed gulls	House sparrows	Common starlings
Enteritidis	16	43.2	68.7	18.7	-	6.2	6.2
Typhimurium	6	16.2	16.7	66.7	16.7	-	-
mST	5	13.5	60	-	20	20	-
Chester	2	5.4	100	-	-	-	-
Infantis	2	5.4	50	-	50	-	-
Kentucky	2	5.4	50	-	50	-	-
Abony	2	5.4	100	-	-	-	-
Pomona	1	2.7	100	-	-	-	-
Saintpaul	1	2.7	-	-	100	-	-
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	37	12.3					

175 n= number of isolates from each serovar.

176

177 **3.1. Prevalence of AMR**

178 For all strains isolated (n=37), 40.5% (n=15) were resistant to at least one of the 12
 179 antimicrobials tested. For white storks, 45.5% (10/22) of the isolated strains were AMR, followed
 180 by common wood pigeons (42.9%, 3/7) and lesser black-backed gulls (20%, 1/5). Moreover,
 181 one of two house sparrows' strains isolated are AMR. It should be noted that the only strain
 182 isolated from common starling was completely susceptible.

183 For all *Salmonella* strains isolated from white storks (n=22), the highest percentage of AMR was
 184 found in CIP and NA (36.4%, respectively), followed by COL (27.3%), TCY (13.6%) and AMP
 185 (9.1%). Moreover, statistical differences were found between the environment inhabited by
 186 white storks and the AMR detected, being landfills where more AMR *Salmonella* strains were
 187 isolated ($p < 0.05$). Regarding lesser black-backed gulls and house sparrows, resistances to
 188 AMP (1/5 and 1/2, respectively) and TCY (1/5 and 1/2, respectively) were found. Finally, for
 189 common wood pigeons, the highest percentage of AMR was found also to CIP (3/7) and NA
 190 (3/7), followed by COL (2/7). No statistical differences were found for UB (except white storks)

191 and the environment they inhabit ($p>0.05$). It is important to highlight that all the isolates were
 192 susceptible to AZM, FOX, CAZ, CHL, GN, MEM, RL, TGC and W. The AMR *Salmonella* strains
 193 isolated per UB species are summarised in Table 2.

194 **Table 2.** Number of *Salmonella* strains isolated with antimicrobial resistance pattern according
 195 to the UB species.

196

Species	n	CIP	NA	AMP	COL	TCY
White storks	10	8	8	2	6	3
Common woodpigeons	3	3	3	-	2	-
Lesser black-backed gulls	1	-	-	1	-	1
House sparrows	1	-	-	1	-	1
Common starlings	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	15	11	11	4	8	5

200

201 n. number of antimicrobial resistant strains, CIP: ciprofloxacin, NA: nalidixic acid, AMP: ampicillin, COL:
 202 colistin, TCY: tetracycline.

203

204 **3.2. Prevalence of multi-drug resistance**

205 From all the resistant isolates (n=15), 86.7% were considered MDR, as they were resistant to at
 206 least one antimicrobial of two different categories. The highest percentage of MDR bacteria was
 207 found for storks (90%, 9/10), followed by common wood pigeons (66.7%, 2/3). Moreover, the
 208 resistant strains isolated from lesser black-backed gulls and house sparrows were multi-
 209 resistant.

210

211 **3.3. Antimicrobial resistance patterns**

212 For white storks, 3 (13.6%) *Salmonella* strains were resistant to two antimicrobials and 7
 213 (31.8%) to three. For common wood pigeons, 4 (57.1%) *Salmonella* isolates were completely
 214 susceptible to all the antimicrobials tested, 1 (14.3%) isolate was resistant to two antimicrobials
 215 and 2 (28.6%) to two. For lesser black-backed gulls, 4 (80.0%) of the isolates were completely

216 susceptible and 1 (20%) was resistant to two antimicrobials. Finally, for house sparrows, 1
217 (50%) *Salmonella* isolate was resistant to two of the antimicrobials tested.

218 Overall, four different resistance patterns were observed. The combination of CIP-NA-COL
219 (n=8, 53.3%) was most frequently observed, followed by the AMP-TCY combination (n=4,
220 26.7%), the CIP-NA combination (n=2, 13.3%) and, finally, the CIP-NA-TCY combination (n=1,
221 6.7%). In this sense, it is important to highlight that 5 of the 8 *S. Enteritidis* isolates from white
222 storks which had access to landfills were multi-resistant and all of them had the resistance
223 pattern CIP-NA-COL.

224

225 4. Discussion

226 Nowadays, cities constitute a shared environment between human and UB, which take
227 advantage of the waste produced by human to feed [4]. The close association between humans
228 and UB facilitates the risks of pathogen dissemination and so their AMR [20,21].

229 The role of UB as a *Salmonella* reservoir is of increasing interest, as wild birds have been
230 outstanding as a source in the dissemination of *Salmonella* spp. [32-34]. Thus, a relationship
231 has been documented between *Salmonella* strains isolated from UB and cattle, livestock and
232 environment [20,24,35,36].

233 This study showed a *Salmonella* prevalence of 12.3% in UB analysed. It is important to highlight
234 the high incidence of *Salmonella* spp. in white storks, especially young birds feeding in landfills
235 [14]. The role of landfills is particularly noteworthy, as they provide UB with a constant source of
236 food. This seems to be particularly evident in white storks and lesser black-backed gulls [5,37],
237 where some researchers have found a relationship between the feeding habits of the birds and
238 the prevalence of bacteria [37,28]. *Salmonella* occurrence in white storks found in this study
239 was in accordance with a recent study carried out in central Spain on white storks that feed in
240 landfills, where 34.8% of animals were *Salmonella*-positive [39]. This fact highlights the role of
241 landfills in the potentiation of wild birds as reservoirs, amplifiers and disseminators of
242 *Salmonella* [32]. Recently, a relationship was demonstrated between farm waste contaminated
243 with *Salmonella* and wild bird infection [40,41]. Contaminated waste from different origins could

244 contaminate landfills and consequently the wild animals that feed from them [35], providing new
245 *Salmonella* pathways from wild animals [33].

246 Young birds have been shown to carry more *Salmonella* than adults [42]. From positive UB,
247 young individuals were shedding the bacteria in 72.9% of cases. This fact may be because of
248 multiple changes in gut microbiota within a short timespan during nestling development, due to
249 the replacement and settling in of more stable bacterial taxa [42,43]. It is important to consider
250 the nest placement effect on the nestling gut microbiota, which gives rise to differences in the
251 bacterial communities. In this line, some UB such as white storks prefer to build their nests near
252 landfills [5,42]. Thus, the *Salmonella* present in landfills would already be affecting chicks from
253 the nest. In addition, if parent faeces or the remains of prey contaminate the nest, the nestlings
254 could become infected with the bacteria [35,42]. In this sense, contamination of environment,
255 agriculture fields or other wild animals by UB is recognised as an important risk factor for the
256 transmission of AMR or pathogens, such as *Salmonella* [44,45].

257 In this study, nine different serovars were isolated from the different UB. Eight of them are
258 considered zoonotic serovars, as they have been isolated in different human salmonellosis
259 outbreaks [22,46,47]. The *Salmonella* serovar most frequently detected in this study was *S.*
260 *Enteritidis*. Previously, the same serovars have been described in free-living bird studies and in
261 domestic animals (poultry and pigs), as well as human outbreaks [22,41,48,49]. In addition,
262 *Salmonella* strains isolated from UB mostly feeding in landfills correspond to serovars
263 commonly isolated in livestock [22,49]. This fact supports the hypothesis that contaminated
264 waste present in landfills is a source of UB *Salmonella* infections. Moreover, the second and
265 third most prevalent serovars isolated in this study, *S. Typhimurium* and mST, have also been
266 described in wild birds related to swine farms as a primary source of *Salmonella* [41,49]. In
267 particular, the mST was initially characterised from pig samples in Spain, and today is
268 considered an emerging pathogen associated with human and swine infections worldwide [49].

269 One of the most relevant results of this study is the level of AMR isolated from UB, especially
270 those than live close to landfills. Recently, there has been increasing interest in resistant
271 bacteria and resistance genes isolated from wildlife and the environment [38,40,41,50]. In our
272 study, the NA-CIP-COL resistance pattern is especially noteworthy. Three antimicrobials are

273 last-resort drugs used to treat human infectious diseases caused by multi-resistant bacteria
274 [16,51]. Interestingly, this study reveals that the risk of AMR strains increases at landfills
275 (21.6%). According to the ecology and habits, UB could be more or less exposed to AMR
276 bacteria and can play an important role in the spread of antimicrobial resistance genes [39,52].
277 Patterns of antimicrobial resistance in UB species may be developed by different factors, such
278 as extensive use in human and/or veterinary medicine, a long time since their introduction in the
279 market, or easy access to antimicrobials [40,52,53]. Overall, these facts confirm a long-lasting
280 and constant selective pressure on environmental bacteria [40,52,53].

281 Resistance to NA and CIP were addressed combined, as they belong to the same class of
282 antimicrobials: quinolones [16]. Both antimicrobials have been widely employed in veterinary
283 medicine to treat infections, as growth promoters and to prevent disease in production animals
284 [52]. In consequence, a statistically significant increase in quinolone resistance has been
285 observed in Spain [16]. These findings are particularly striking, as quinolones are synthetic
286 antimicrobials, so bacteria have no natural resistance mechanism. Therefore, the spread of
287 resistance to quinolones should be limited [52]. Furthermore, COL had been widely applied in
288 food-producing animals over the years, but its use is now very restricted in animal health, as it
289 represents the last line of defence against pan-resistant infections in humans. Despite the
290 measures carried out to reduce the consumption of antimicrobials, the percentage of COL-
291 resistant strains in UB that feed on landfills is critical and represent an important risk of colistin
292 resistance spread. It is important to highlight that environmental bacteria may obtain resistance
293 genes from resistant bacteria or from natural sources of antimicrobials, including urban
294 environments [40,50,52]. Other studies reported that the resistance might easily transferred to
295 microbiota bacteria, or to environmental bacteria, which can act as reservoirs and be a source
296 of AMR [54]. In this context, the scientific community, public administration and the population in
297 general should work together to control antimicrobial administration and drug waste
298 management in order to minimise the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance.

299

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309

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Table 1.Percentage of each *Salmonella* serovar isolated by species.

<i>Salmonella</i> serovars	n	Total (%)	Species (%)				
			White storks	Common wood pigeons	Lesser black- backed gulls	House sparrows	Common starlings
Enteritidis	16	43.2	68.7	18.7	-	6.2	6.2
Typhimurium	6	16.2	16.7	66.7	16.7	-	-
mST	5	13.5	60	-	20	20	-
Chester	2	5.4	100	-	-	-	-
Infantis	2	5.4	50	-	50	-	-
Kentucky	2	5.4	50	-	50	-	-
Abony	2	5.4	100	-	-	-	-
Pomona	1	2.7	100	-	-	-	-
Saintpaul	1	2.7	-	-	100	-	-
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	37	12.3					

n= number of isolates from each serovar.

Table 2. Number of *Salmonella* strains isolated with antibiotic resistance pattern according to the UB species.

Species	n	CIP	NA	AMP	COL	TCY
White storks	10	8	8	2	6	3
Common woodpigeons	3	3	3	-	2	-
Lesser black-backed gulls	1	-	-	1	-	1
House sparrows	1	-	-	1	-	1
Common starlings	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	15	11	11	4	8	5

n. number of antibiotic resistant strains, CIP: ciprofloxacin, NA: nalidixic acid, AMP: ampicillin, COL: colistin, TCY: tetracycline.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

Manuscript title: Landfills: an important source of antimicrobial resistant Salmonella for urban birds

The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Author names:

Bárbara Martín-Maldonado
Santiago Vega
Aida Mencía-Gutiérrez
Laura Lorenzo-Rebenaque
Cristina de Frutos
Fernando Gonzalez
Luis Revuelta
Clara Marin

The authors whose names are listed immediately below report the following details of affiliation or involvement in an organization or entity with a financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript. Please specify the nature of the conflict on a separate sheet of paper if the space below is inadequate.

Author names:

This statement is signed by all the authors to indicate agreement that the above information is true and correct (a photocopy of this form may be used if there are more than 10 authors):

Author's name (typed)	Author's signature	Date
<u>Bárbara Martín-Maldonado</u>		<u>09/10/19</u>
<u>Santiago Vega</u>		<u>09/10/19</u>
<u>Aída Mencía-Gutiérrez</u>		<u>11/10/19</u>
<u>Laura Lorenzo-Rebenaque</u>	Firmado por Laura Lorenzo Rebenaque	<u>09/10/19</u>
<u>Cristina de Frutos</u>		<u>09/10/19</u>
<u>Fernando González</u>	Firmado por FERNANDO GONZALEZ GONZALEZ el día 12/10/2019 con un certificado emitido por	<u>09/10/19</u>
<u>Luis Revuelta</u>	Luis Revuelta Rueda	Firmado digitalmente por Luis Revuelta Rueda Nombre de reconocimiento (DN): cn=Luis Revuelta Rueda, o=Universidad Complutense de Madrid, ou, email=lrevuel@vet.ucm.es, c=ES Fecha: 2019.10.09 17:11:32 +02'00'
<u>Clara Marin</u>		<u>09/10/2019</u>
<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
<u> </u>	<u> </u>	<u> </u>

Credit author statement

Bárbara Martín-Maldonado: Methodology, Investigation and Writing – Original Draft. **Santiago Vega:** Conceptualisation and Visualisation and Funding Acquisition. **Aida Mencía-Gutiérrez:** Methodology. **Laura Lorenzo-Rebenaque:** Writing – Review & Editing. **Cristina de Frutos:** Methodology and Writing – Review & Editing. **Fernando González:** Resources and Funding Acquisition. **Luis Revuelta:** Resources. **Clara Marin:** Formal Analysis, Validation, Resources, Supervision and Project Administration.